

MICRO-MECHANICAL MODELS FOR THE TRANSVERSE PROPERTIES
OF HIGH TEMPERATURE METAL-MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

One problem with all composites is predicting the properties of the lamina from the properties of its constituents. For some high temperature metal-matrix composites, this problem is complicated by the formation of a reaction zone between the fiber and the matrix. Transverse properties are harder to predict than longitudinal ones. A model for predicting the transverse modulus was developed by Hopkins and Chamis at NASA-Lewis. This paper presents the development of two more refined models for predicting this property. In the first model some intermediate steps are eliminated and the required integrations performed directly. The second approach is based on a concentric cylinder model and a theory of elasticity approach. Results from both methods are compared to the Hopkins-Chamis approach. These comparisons indicate that the more complicated models presented in this study are valid and more useful than the previous model in some cases.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Metal-Matrix; Micromechanics; Elevated Temperature; Transverse Modulus.

1. INTRODUCTION

Predicting the mechanical properties of a composite

material system based on the known properties of its constituents is necessary. This study is concerned with predicting the transverse modulus, especially for metal-matrix composites at elevated temperatures. This problem is sometimes complicated by the formation of a reaction zone or interface between the fiber and the matrix for many metal-matrix composites. An example of such a material is tungsten fiber reinforced superalloys (TFRS). This reaction zone introduces a third phase or constituent.

A set of micromechanical models for predicting the properties of composites with reaction zones has been developed [1]. A mechanics of materials approach was used to find the transverse modulus. The Hopkins-Chamis model took a square as the unit cell as shown in Figure 1. The circular regions of the fiber and the reaction zone were transformed into squares of equal area. The transverse modulus is given by:

$$E_{22} = E_m \left[1 - \sqrt{k_f} + \frac{\sqrt{k_f} \left(1 - \frac{D}{D_0} \right)}{1 - \sqrt{k_f} \left(1 - \frac{E_m}{E_{rz}} \right)} + \frac{\sqrt{k_f} \left(\frac{D}{D_0} \right)}{1 - \sqrt{k_f} \left(1 - \left(1 - \frac{D}{D_0} \right) \frac{E_m}{E_{rz}} - \left(\frac{D}{D_0} \right) \frac{E_m}{E_f} \right)} \right] \quad (1)$$

where the subscripts refer to the fiber, matrix and reaction zone, and k_f is the fiber volume fraction.

This paper presents two alternatives to the above equation. The first alternative is very similar except that it does not replace the fiber and reaction zone with equivalent square areas. This requires evaluating several integrals. The second approach is drastically different and is based on an entirely different unit cell, as shown in Figure 2. This approach is based on some theory of elasticity results.

In the subsequent sections these two models are outlined in some detail and results are presented. These results are compared with those from the Hopkins-Chamis model.

2. RECTANGULAR CELL INTEGRATION MODEL

The most obvious improvement that can be made to the Hopkins-Chamis model is the elimination of the transformation to equivalent square areas. This transformation is simply for analytical convenience and has no theoretical foundation. The method proposed herein takes an elemental strip (Figure 3.) distance y from the x -axis with the modulus is given by:

Figure 1. Unit Cell for Hopkins-Chamis and Rectangular Cell Integration Models

Figure 2. Unit Cell for Circular Cell Elasticity Model

$$E_{strip} = \frac{1}{\left[\frac{1}{E_m} \left(\frac{l_m}{a_1} \right) + \frac{1}{E_{rz}} \left(\frac{l_{rz}}{a_1} \right) + \frac{1}{E_f} \left(\frac{l_f}{a_1} \right) \right]} \quad (2)$$

where the dimensions l_r etc. are all given in Figure 3. and are all functions of y . The ply thickness can be found from D_0 and k_r . Expressions for the l 's are given in Table 1. The modulus for the composite is then the integral of Equation 1. over the entire width of the layer. This integral will be broken up into three parts:

$$E_{22} = 2 \left[\frac{\left(\int_0^{D/2} E_{strip} dy + \int_{D/2}^{D_0/2} E_{strip} dy + \int_{D_0/2}^{a_1} E_{strip} dy \right)}{a_1} \right] \quad (3)$$

When values for the l 's from Table 1. are substituted into Equation 2. and integrated in Equation 3. some complicated integrals result. Numerical integration is the only practical way in which to solve this set of integrals. A computer program was written which quickly and accurately evaluates the necessary integrals need by Equation 3. to evaluate E_{22} . Since any micromechanical model is typically evaluated on a computer, the need for numerical integration does not make this approach too cumbersome.

Figure 3. Schematic of RCI Model

TABLE 1. EXPRESSIONS FOR LENGTH TERMS

	$0 \leq y \leq D/2$	$D/2 \leq y \leq D_0/2$	$D_0/2 \leq y \leq a_1/2$
l_f	$2((D/2)^2 - y^2)^{1/2}$	0	0
l_{rz}	$2((D_0/2)^2 - y^2)^{1/2} - l_f$	$2((D_0/2)^2 - y^2)^{1/2}$	0
l_m	$a_1 - l_f - l_{rz}$	$a_1 - 2((D_0/2)^2 - y^2)^{1/2}$	a_1

3. CIRCULAR CELL ELASTICITY MODEL

A completely different approach was also tried. This procedure starts with a circular unit cell as shown in Figure 2. The concentric cylinders are subjected to a radial compressive stress as shown in Figure 4. Displacement continuity is enforced at the interfaces. The displacement for a hollow circular cylinder subjected to an axial load is well known. The displacement continuity conditions at $r = D/2$ and $r = D_0/2$ supply the conditions needed to calculate the pressure terms P' and P'' (see Figure 4.). An expression for the displacement of the outer wall is then obtained. Once this value is known, it is assumed that the composite cylinders behave as an homogeneous solid cylinder. Equating the displacement of the homogeneous solid cylinder with that obtained previously for the composite gives:

$$u_{comp} = P_0 \left(\frac{(1 - \nu_c)}{E_{22}} \right) \frac{a_1}{2} \quad (4)$$

where u_{comp} is the displacement for the composite as calculated from the concentric cylinder approach, P_0 is the external pressure, a_1 is the diameter of the circular cell, and E_{22} and ν_c are the transverse modulus and in-plane Poisson's ratio of the composite. Typically the pressure and displacement are known. If the Poisson's ratio is known then E_{22} can be obtained from Equation 4. If the Poisson's ratio is not known then an additional condition is needed. This can be obtained by considering the concentric cylinders shown in Figure 2. to be subjected to a torsional load. The angle of twist of the components is assumed to be equal by continuity. If T_0 is the external torque, and T' and T'' are the torques at the interfaces (similar to P' and P'' in the preceding analysis) then:

Figure 4. Pressure Distributions for CCE Model

$$\frac{T_0 - T''}{J_m G_m} = \frac{T'' - T'}{J_{rz} G_{rz}} = \frac{T'}{J_f G_f} = \frac{T_0}{J_{comp} G_{comp}} \quad (5)$$

where G represents the shear modulus of each component and J represents the polar moment of inertia. Equation 5 can be solved for G_{comp} in terms of known quantities:

$$G_{comp} = \frac{G_m J_m + G_{rz} J_{rz} + G_f J_f}{J_{comp}} \quad (6)$$

If the equivalent homogeneous ply is assumed to have in-plane isotropy then:

$$G_{comp} = \frac{E_{22}}{2(1 + \nu_c)} \quad (7)$$

Combining Equations 4. and 6. then gives the Poisson' Ratio as:

$$v_c = \frac{\frac{(P_0 a_1)}{2 u_c} - 2 G_{comp}}{\frac{(P_0 a_1)}{2 u_c} + 2 G_{comp}} \quad (8)$$

and this value can be substituted into Equation 4. to get E_{22} . The Circular Cell Elasticity model offers the advantage of including the Poisson's effect in calculating E_{22} and indeed allows the Poisson's ratio itself to be calculated.

4. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Results for both of the previously described models were obtained for a tungsten fiber reinforced superalloy (TFRS) metal matrix composite. Material properties for the fiber and matrix are given in Table 2. for room temperature and an elevated temperature (1100 °C). The properties of the reaction zone were taken to be the average of the fiber and the matrix values.

In Figure 5. results for the rectangular cell integration are presented for the high temperature properties as a function of reaction zone size for several fiber volume ratios. These results are identical to those from the Hopkins-Chamis model. The fact that these two methods coincide validates the Hopkins-Chamis model. The simplifying transformation to equivalent square areas does not appear to introduce significant errors. That transformation does allow an expression for the transverse modulus to be written in closed form instead of requiring numerical integration. Based on these results the existing Hopkins-Chamis model is preferred over the rectangular cell integration model.

Results for the circular cell integration model are compared to the Hopkins-Chamis results in Figure 6. for the same case as presented in Figure 5. These results show some noticeable differences between the two methods especially for the higher fiber volume ratios. The difference in the modulus value can be as high as 10% in some cases. It is possible to study the influence of the Poisson's effect by setting the Poisson's ratios of the constituent materials equal to zero and repeating the calculations for the circular cell model. The influence of the Poisson's effect is studied in Figure 7. As can be seen, the influence is noticeable. The difference in the

Figure 5. Comparison of Predicted Transverse Modulus Values from Rectangular Cell Integration and Hopkins-Chamis Models.

Figure 6. Comparison of Predicted Transverse Modulus Values from Circular Cell Elasticity and Hopkins-Chamis Models.

TABLE 2. MATERIAL PROPERTIES				
PROPERTY	ROOM TEMPERATURE		HIGH TEMPERATURE	
	FIBER	MATRIX	FIBER	MATRIX
E (GPa)	359	208	317	109
G (GPa)	139	80	123	42
ν	.29	.30	.29	.30

Figure 7. Comparison of Predicted Transverse Modulus Values from Circular Cell Elasticity With and Without Poisson's Effects.

modulus is about 3% and seems to be fairly consistent throughout the entire range of fiber volume ratios and reaction zone sizes.

A drawback to the circular cell model is the fact that a lamina cannot be produced by a collection of circular cells. It is felt that the difficulties presented by this fact do not invalidate the results for this model. If additional matrix material is used to fill in the gaps a decrease in the fiber volume ratio results. Since the circular cell model is already predicting lower results for the same fiber volume ratio than the Hopkins-Chamis model, the presence of more matrix material would lead to even lower values.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In examining this work, several conclusions can be drawn. These conclusions can be summarized as follows:

1. The transformation to equivalent square areas in the Hopkins-Chamis model does not appear to introduce any noticeable errors in the results.
2. The circular cell model offers the advantage of also providing the Poisson's ratio as well as the transverse modulus.
3. The influence of the Poisson's effect appears to be somewhat limited.
4. The models presented herein are theoretically more accurate than the Hopkins-Chamis model. However, the difference in the results are often less than the errors in the constituent material properties. Thus, the simpler Hopkins-Chamis model is preferred in most instances. The results herein validate many of the assumptions and simplification of the Hopkins-Chamis model and increase the confidence in that model.

6. REFERENCES

1. D.A. Hopkins and C.C. Chamis, "A Unique Set of Micromechanics Equations for High Temperature Metal Matrix Composites", NASA TM-87154, 1985.